

a Top 25 improvements and decrements across structures when comparing CT-FM with random initialization

b Performance of models when comparing select structures with properties- large, smooth, small, irregular shape

Extended Data Figure 1: Additional comparisons between CT-FM and baselines on segmentation of anatomical structures in whole-body CT scans.

a Few-shot performance (number of samples to train) across different structure groups in TotalSegmentator dataset

Extended Data Figure 2: Few-shot performance considering structure groups across the TotalSegmentator dataset

a Patient-wise comparison of MSD tumor segmentation results and visualization of failure cases across approaches.

Extended Data Figure 3: Detailed patient-wise breakdown of comparisons on the MSD dataset with failure cases visualized.

a Content-based retrieval precision for k=3, 5 and 10 and overall average precision for the presence of a lesion on different anatomies of the 3D-MIR dataset

Extended Data Figure 4: Content-based retrieval detailed results for anatomical regions

a Comparison of anatomical clustering of CT-FM with baseline SuPREM across different values of perplexity

Extended Data Figure 5: Comparison of anatomical clustering between CT-FM and baseline

a Ablation of pre-training strategies evaluated on few-shot whole body segmentation on the TotalSegmentator dataset

b Ablation of number of crops on few-shot whole body segmentation

c Evolution of representation quality for whole body segmentation during the pre-training process.

d Semantic concept matching between query patch and two selected target scans

Extended Data Figure 6: Pre-training ablations and evolution of representation quality during pre-training

a Stability of patch embeddings on the RIDER test-retest dataset evaluated through cosine similarity

b Stability of patch embeddings on the RIDER test-retest dataset evaluated through mean squared error

Extended Data Figure 7: Stability of CT-FM embeddings compared patch-wise between the RIDER dataset test-retest scans.

a Contrastive learning scenario for batch with limited variance between instances when compared to variance between views

b Reformulation of the contrastive learning objective for limited variance medical imaging contexts

p_{0-n} Patches sampled from scan

T^x Transformations to generate views

$f(x)$ SegResNet encoder

512-dimensional representation

● Projected representation

Extended Data Figure 8: Intra-sample pre-training adaptation for SimCLR

Extended Data Figure 9: Semantic search app workflow. Steps in the process are 1) select the source scan; 2) select the slice of interest; 3) select the target scan; 4) select a point around a region of interest in the source scan around which a 3D box will be cropped; 5) Run the semantic search framework to obtain the results